

Economic Impact of Covid-19 Restrictions on Resort Industry in Indang, Cavite

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Abstract:- The research relates to resort businesses in Indang that have a socio-economic influence on Covid-19. The study is a qualitative research, and the chosen resorts are well known in Indang, thanks to the assistance of the owners of these resorts. The quantitative technique is used in this study to measure attitudes, behaviors, and other categorical characteristics and to simplify the results for a larger population. To acquire the essential data, survey questions are used. Also, to calculate the total number of respondents, a statistical processing approach was used in data collection. The average technique of weight and ranges are used for economic impacts. To answer the

I. INTRODUCTION

Indang Cavite is one of the places sufferings from the COVID-19 pandemic, affecting markets, livelihoods, infrastructure, and opportunities on all continents. The facts are clear that this pandemic has plenty of negative effects in every industry and workplace, especially in the tourism industry. It includes reducing places to go to like beaches, hotels, and resorts, traveling in several countries and cities in terms of economic impact, following new protocols and guidelines by the govt., observing, isolating that is infected, and taking swab tests whenever one wants to travel outside. Still, the government continues to find ways to control this pandemic so the attractions and lifestyle of the many will bring back to what they used to be. Indang could be a settlement within the Philippines that will be visited in an exceedingly single day. It is a historic and beautiful province that is ideal for both business and pleasure. During this city, there are few things to try to or places to determine. Since it is a little town, there are fewer lodging options. People usually consider stopping here for a brief break before continuing to the neighboring cities. You will stop for a brief snack and an opening from your journey here. While this is often a little town, resorts are scattered altogether 32 Barangays. Since it is a well-liked tourist destination, it is best to go to the resort during the week.

According to GMA News Online, while there's Covid 19 Pandemic, there is a resort in Indang Cavite that plenty of tourists went there without noticing of preventing physical distancing. Young and old people gathered within the streets or within the cottages, which were often crowded. Many visitors were seen without their face shields and mask. It also connects to Republic Act 9593 or Tourism Act of 2009, that the DOT is chargeable for enacting formalities that regulate the activity and activities of all tourism businesses. In which, the government and tourism sectors are authorized to implement rules and regulations to destinations to stay the tourist attractions protected. The IATF (Inter-Agency Task Force) for the Organization of Emerging Transferrable

questions, the researchers have modified online learning and are using Google Forms as a data collection tool. The researchers use the social media platform to share the link to the survey form. Out of ethical consideration, the researchers wrote a letter to a formal conduct or survey questionnaire. This research aims to help the resort economy in this circumstance, especially in Indang, Cavite, by conducting a survey and analyzing the situation to implement a long-term strategy.

Keywords: Economic impacts, Covid-19, Resorts.

Diseases Compilation Guidelines on the Application of Community Quarantine in the Philippines defines the "New Normal" as "emerging attitudes, circumstances, and community health standards" that will be established in common or routine practices and can last long after the pandemic has passed, according to the Department of Tourism's official website. While the virus cannot be completely eradicated by means like mass vaccination, a requirement to incorporate recommendations is needed to send revised health and safety procedures within the procedures of accommodation establishments within the New Normal Situation.

As per the article titled "GDP Growth Hits 8-Year Low in 2019," In the first half of 2019, the Philippines' economy grew at a slower rate. The country's GDP grew at a steady 6.3 percent between 2010 and 2018, before falling to 5.5% in the first half of 2019. The Philippines' economy is projected to rise 5.8% this year. The coronavirus outbreak could have a big effect on the Philippine economy within the coming months. If it lasts six months, it could cost the Philippine economy \$600 million, or 0.8 percent of GDP. According to the Department of Tourism (DOT) (2020) when it involves accommodation establishments, visitors must fill out a Health Declaration Form upon arrival, and eligible health or medical control or skilled personnel must conduct temperature checks employing a thermal electronic scanner at the entrances for all guests. Only cleared guests by security are going to be able to access the boundary to test in. Those with an illness or flu-like symptoms are not allowed and can be said to the assigned doctor, the closest hospital, or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (BHERT) as per DOH protocol. Huge impacts are being experienced on the macro and micro levels of tourism sectors. Relative to the overall level, it disrupts the provision chain, particularly in Cavite, and result in the loss of jobs and other businesses its outlook growth. At the micro-level, transportation, accommodation, resort industries were affected drastically. The vulnerable and poor are greatly affected regarding the loss of income, deterioration in livelihoods, and well-being. As tourism

students, it is the will of the researchers to find out more about the consequences of the Covid-19 Pandemic, especially on tourist destinations, particularly the resort, which is the focus of this study.

During this case, the research aims to assess the economic impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the resorts in Indang, Cavite as a part of a proposed long-term strategy. It will aim to attain subsequent goals:

- To measure the economic impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic within the resort of Indang Cavite that affects the business with regards to sales, revenue, employment, wage and salary, and financial conditions.
- To ascertain the differences in the respondents' assessment of the economic impact within the resort that affects the business due to the Covid-19 Pandemic when grouped in line with the profile.
- To propose an economically sustainable plan.

The researchers found out that other sections of the resort's economy are infected with the COVID-19 pandemic. This study will look at how the virus affects a tourist attraction like a resort, which can provide information and link it to other tourist destinations in the area. Indang will also reflect destinations that have been affected by COVID-19 in terms of economic position. This type of research is important since it is timely and is now taking place in our tourism business.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The literature review is one of the important parts of the study. The data included under the literature review were connected to the entire study to see current updates that connect with the Resorts of Indang Cavite. The entire discussions are the idea of the researcher compiled to such essential information that became helpful for the study. The results of the gathered data are the guide of the researcher throughout reporting of the topic matter. COVID-19 is having financial failure to some prominent brands in numerous projects as the clients' lodge at home base and economies are shut down (Tucker, 2020). In the US, prominent groups like JCPenney, Sears, Hertz, Neiman Marcus, and J. Group are under economic hardship. The tourism industry is extremely hit; 80% of accommodations are unoccupied (Asmelash and Cooper, 2020), carriers their workforce at 90% and travel business concerns are not likely to determine repayment in 2020. Furthermore, games, meetings, exhibitions, and other huge events such as social foundations, displays, and historical centers are canceled. Individual administrations like stylists, exercise centers, and taxicabs, are also prohibited due to quarantine. There are a few inquiries that could pose in association with this sudden lockdown. For instance, how could we cater for work in these circumstances? Why can organizations not handle such circumstances (e.g., putting aside profit or considering alternative earnings)? How are organizations as well as nations utilizing this circumstance to upgrade this serious circumstance?

(Rapoza, 2020). As stated in the International Development Law Organization, there is an application of Enhanced Community Quarantine policies that involves strict control, police-military checkpoints, postponement of public transport, and closing companies and government services (Rimando M. 2020). As the last update in keeping with the Municipality of Indang, on March 18, 2021, there are 510 reported cases and 39 active cases. Indang remains promoting following such safety guidelines to decrease stated numbers.

The effect on the MSME's SALES study traced down 59.9% of micro-enterprises in March 2020. Because of the short-term closing of the company, trailed with small companies (44.8%) along with average companies (35.8%), recommending real effect on micro-enterprises. MSMEs that worked constantly during the lockdown encountered vital call deals: 27.7% miniature, 43.6% small, and 41.0% average-sized companies which encountered a business decline of 30% in March since February (a month before lockdown). Each area—administrations, assembling, and farming had no deals on following the lockdown (the bigger component of MSMEs in each area). Because several MSMEs had a deal expansion due to request through the lockdown, as an example, selling exchange offering everyday merchandise and goods.

The effect on MSME REVENUE happened just like the outcomes for MSME agreements. It has 61.7% of micro-enterprises without salary in March 2020 because of business terminations, supported by small companies (49.1%) plus average companies (35.8%). MSMEs that worked during the lockdown had an intense call income including 26.5% miniature, 40.8% small, and 41.0% medium-sized companies having a 30% income decline during March since February. All three modern areas do not have revenue after the lockdown (60% of MSMEs in governments as well as assembly). Certain gatherings of MSMEs extended their income because of extraordinary interest due to the lockdown. In general, many MSMEs EMPLOYMENT encountered lockdown (65.7% miniature, 50.8% small, then 66.3% average companies). However, MSMEs started decreasing representatives from the start to continue (68.0% miniature, 59.5% small, and 78.6% average companies) particularly in assembling (69.4%) and administrations (67.3%). The bigger the company scope, the more extra working choices were available. Along with average-sized companies, 41.1% reduced their worker's working hours, then 34.8% small companies along with 26.5% micro-enterprises. Minor firms had lots of trouble in introducing this course of action: 24.9% average, 19.8% small, and 11.3% of micro-enterprises.

An enormous part of MSMEs has been postponed WAGE PAYMENT to representatives after the Coronavirus and quarantine, and this was more obvious for micro-enterprises (59.8%) and buildings (61.0%). Around 30% of small and average activities are declined within the full compensation payments to representatives

after the incident. Over 20% of MSMEs in assembling agricultural businesses decreased their wage expenses. Most MSMEs came up short on the economic situation and wanted to maintain their business after the quarantine. The aspects in terms of capital loss were more genuine in adding companies. It has 43.8% of miniature, 23.2% small, and 3.9% standard-sized projects without money or spare funds at the hour of the overview. Furthermore, 61.4% of standard-sized, 53.1% of small, and 37.8% of micro-enterprises announced that there are finished assets in a very month. Just 14.8% of miniature, 19.0% of small,

and 28.7% of the standard-sized company had enough capital and investment to make all the difference of business for a month. Each of the areas faced a scarcity of assets. There have been 43.7% of administration MSMEs without money or funds, trailed by agricultural (42.1%) as well as producing MSMEs (34.2%). MSMEs (47.8%) stated that their assets have ended in 30 days, trailed by administrations (37.4%) and cultivation (35.1%). Around 22.5% of agricultural MSMEs showed that there are sufficient money and properties to remain in their company for a month.

Fig. 1: Conceptual framework.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative method because it is used to review opinions, behaviors, and other categorical variables and is used to simplify the findings of a larger population. The researchers also selected several resorts: Alta Rios Resort (2013), Siglo Paraiso Farm Resort (2019), Villa Colmenar Natural Spring Resort (2017), Carasuchi Villa (201), Rio Villa Nuevo Mineral Water Resort (1993), and Villa Filomena. Natural Spring Resort (2017) to collect information for this study. A pre-test was conducted with 30 resort owners to check the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire. Once approved by the statistician, the researchers collected data from 100 respondents representing the total population of resort owners in Indang, Cavite.

Researchers apply samples of descriptions and designs. The questioner is the owner of the statistics stations because they have the main source and related information on the economic impact of the Covid19 limitations in the Indang and Cavite stations industry. Survey questionnaires are also used to collect required data. The percentage method has been used in the investigation questionnaire to understand the answers collected from the respondent. The investigation is divided into 2 parts: gender, age, and educational level of participants. For the second part, they must answer the questions divided into options: Agree, fully agree, disagree, fully disagree. Researchers have also used a frequency method and percentage for respondents. In addition, a statistical processing method is also used in data collection to determine the total number of respondents. For economic impacts, weighted and averaged methods are used. The researchers adapted the e-learning and used the Google form as a data collection tool to answer the questions provided. Survey form link is distributed by researchers through social media platform.

The researchers arranged a letter to a formal manner of survey questionnaire for ethical consideration. The letter was emailed to avoid direct contact with individuals and to keep respondents and the entire data collection process confidential. Legal letters have been forwarded to owners or managers of specific stations to notify them of the collection of information of this concern. The validity of the questionnaire was checked. The researchers introduced him to a statistician, an advisor, and board members. All questions regarding the economic impact of Covid19 restrictions for the Indang resort industry. Researchers statistically scrutinized and explained the information gathered from the survey. Different results have been presented in tables to summarize and analyze data collected to easily identify differences with each other. The statistical instruments utilized in the quantitative investigation of the study have been depicted by insights like frequency, rate, median, and standard deviation.

IV. RESULTS

A. Interpretation for Gender:

The table shows the least number of beach resort owners in Indang Cavite who are women. It shows that 43% are women. While this rate in men is 57%. In this category, the greater area is men, which means more male owners than women. The total is 100% for the combined numbers from the overall survey for this category.

GENDER	Frequency	Percent
FEMALE	43	43.0
MALE	57	57.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1: Demographic Profile of The Respondents

B. Interpretation for Age:

The table shows that the fewest respondents are between the ages of 30 and 39, representing 18% of the total number of respondents. The most successful owners are between the ages of 20 and 29. The conclusion of a total of 100% gives the aggregate numbers of the overall survey in this category.

AGE	Frequency	Percent
20 - 29	41	41.0
30 - 39	18	18.0
40 - 49	22	22.0
50 ABOVE	19	19.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2

C. Interpretation for Educational Attainment:

The respondents had at least a master's degree, representing 34% Of the absolute number of respondents. While the bachelor's degree corresponds to 66% of the respondents. It just means that some of the owners already have a master's degree. Conclusion of 100% total quantities of the general overview for this classification.

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	66	66.0
Master's degree	34	34.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3: Assessments of Economic Impact of Covid-19 in Sales

SALES	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The resort gets a good response from its prospects in terms of sales.	2.80	.696	Agree	2
Sales are still stable during the pandemic.	2.50	.772	Agree	5
The resort is stable to operate even in pandemic season.	2.57	.728	Agree	4
The resort’s number of sales is increasing even in times of pandemic.	2.60	.725	Agree	3
The resort strictly monitors the number of sales.	3.29	.591	Agree	1
Overall mean for Sales	2.752	.5126	High Impact	

Table 4

Another result of the table is shown in Table 2. This shows the average weighted method, standard deviation, explanation, and verbal ratings. In terms of sales, end assessment points rank 5. This article has the smallest number of agreements in this category. It only means that people are asked to agree less that sales are always stable in the pandemic. It has a 2.50 average response and a standard deviation of 0.772. On average it implies that respondents have a significant impact on sales. The overall average is 2.752, with standard deviations of 0.5126. The results relate to this study (Abdelnour, Babbitz, and Moss 2020) that most companies are going through a sharp decline and

unusual demand. It is also said that the crisis also causes unexpected and unusual insistence on demand and prices, sometimes increasing, but often going to a pandemic. In many fields, air transit to durable and non-durable goods, net demand, redundancy, and rates increase to converge prices to support prices and pull-down merit. What's more for this, numerous clients require a markdown and dealings as indicated by the agreement, while certain contenders settle on choices regarding forceful costs. Yet, they won't endorse it so deals will diminish more if they begin making it happen.

REVENUE	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The resort gains revenue even in pandemic.	2.56	.686	Agree	4
The resort maintains its revenue even in pandemic.	2.54	.688	Agree	5
There is flexibility in the resort’s revenue.	3.29	.574	Agree	1
The resort’s lists of revenue keep its confidentiality.	3.26	.613	Agree	2
The resort has strategies and gives consideration when it comes to its revenue.	3.25	.592	Agree	3
Overall mean for Revenue	2.980	.4095	High Impact	

Table 5: Assessments of Economic Impact of Covid-19 in Revenue

Table 3 shows the evaluation of the economic impact of Covid19 on sales. Rank 5 is the lowest level with an average of 2.54 and the standard deviation is 0.688. This article has the smallest number of agreements in this category. This means that respondents agree less that the resort maintains its revenue even in the pandemic. The average implies that respondents have a significant impact on income. The overall mean is 2.980, with a standard deviation of 0.4095. The findings are tied to this study

(Sheiner and Campbell, 2020) that there is a large variation in tax loss related to COVID. Country and regional tax income are predicted to reduce by 0.7% in 2020, 7.5% in 2021, and 7.7% in 2022: \$22 billion, \$37 billion, and \$37 billion, respectively. 0 billion USD. These moderate declines, especially compared with estimated declines in previous recessions, reflect the low incomes of most unemployed workers and the generous tax incentives outlined above.

EMPLOYMENT	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The resort gives support for employed workers.	3.31	.526	Agree	1
There is job security in terms of employment in resorts.	3.16	.721	Agree	5
There are proper guidelines and protocols for safety of personnel in the area of employment in the resort.	3.22	.645	Agree	4
In terms of employment, the resort provides enough resources (Equipment, time, people, and money) to the employees.	3.26	.597	Agree	2
Fair treatment is implemented in the area of employment in the resort.	3.25	.592	Agree	3
Overall mean for Employment	3.240	.5700	High Impact	

Table 6: Assessments of Economic Impact of Covid-19 in Employment

Table 4 presents an assessment of the economic impact of Covid19 on employment. Rank 5 is the lowest with a mean of 3.16 and a standard deviation of 0.721. This item has the fewest deals in this category. This means that respondents are less likely to agree that there is job security in terms of recruitment at the station. The overall average implies that respondents have a high impact on employment. The overall mean is 3.240, with a standard deviation of 0.5700. The findings are related to this study (Cagahastian, 2016) that Acting Provost of the College of

Labor and Industrial Relations at the University of the Philippines (UP Solair) believes that the layoff plan will lead to increased spending on health services. SMEs in the range of 200 to 300 pesos per employee per month. Tolentino also said promoting job security for workers gives them the job security provided for by the bill of rights. "If there is job security, employee satisfaction will increase. Tolentino says there will be fewer strikes and layoffs, so there will be more productivity.

WAGE PAYMENT	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The resort implements wage payment on time.	3.24	.605	Agree	4
There is overtime pay in the resort.	3.25	.626	Agree	3
Equal Pay is implemented in the rules of wage payment of the resort.	3.23	.601	Agree	5
There are accurate time records in wage payment of the resort.	3.26	.630	Agree	2
On-time payroll processing is implemented in terms of wage payment in the resort.	3.27	.584	Agree	1
Overall mean for Wage Payment	3.250	.5515	High Impact	

Table 7: Assessments of Economic Impact of Covid-19 in Wage payment

Table 5 shows the economic impact assessment of Covid19 in terms of payment. Section 5 is classified at the lowest level with an average of 3.23 and a standard deviation of .601. This article has the lowest deal in this category. This means that people who are asked are less appropriate than the equivalent remuneration level are carried out in payroll settlement rules. The general average implies that respondents have a significant impact on payment. The overall mean is 3.250, with a standard deviation of 0.5515. The findings are related to this study

(International Labor Organization, 2020) that about a third of the entire Philippine workforce is working in a vulnerable situation. Vulnerable workers, d. H. Those who help family members and the self-employed are generally lower paid, have low levels of job security, and are more likely to face occupational hazards. Vulnerable employment, as well as part-time work, is common in sectors with moderate to high risk of COVID-19 shutdowns, including transportation and warehousing, housing, and hotels, as well as wholesale and retail trade.

FINANCIAL CONDITION	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The resort is doing their calculating financial differences.	3.23	.617	Agree	2.5
The resort has a financial statement that reflects in real time.	3.25	.592	Agree	1
The resort has good financial condition for the business to sustain.	2.74	.691	Agree	5
The resort is prepared for liquidity of cash flows.	3.07	.685	Agree	4
There is revising of procedures in the records of financial condition to prevent its discrepancies.	3.23	.601	Agree	2.5
Overall mean for Financial Condition	3.104	.4605	High Impact	
Overall Impact	3.0652	0.4367	High Impact	

Table 6: Assessments of Economic Impact of Covid-19 in financial condition

Table 6 shows the evaluation of the economic impact of Covid19 on financial conditions. Rank 5 has the lowest with an average of 2.74 and standard deviations of 0.691. This article has the lowest deal in this category. This means that the respondents agree to less than a good financial terminal for the company to be maintained. The average implies that respondents have a high impact on financial status. The total average is 3.104 with a standard deviation of .4605. For the general average of all designated

categories (sales, revenue, employment, payment, financial conditions), there are 3.0652 and standard deviations are 0.4367. The results related to this study (Farrell, Wheat, and Mac, 2020) that small businesses are affected by Covid19 in a monetary aspect. Financial companies are more vulnerable, with lower income and less liquidity than Willow town companies. Therefore, they can be more likely to be more negative shocks, especially if they also work in highly affected industries.

A. In Terms of Gender

T-TEST RESULT

GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	p-value	Interpretation	
Sales	MALE	57	2.747	.5392	-0.018	0.918	Not Significant.
	FEMALE	43	2.758	.4812			
Revenue	MALE	57	3.014	.4373	0.0792	0.341	Not Significant.
	FEMALE	43	2.935	.3696			
Employment	MALE	57	3.365	.6212	0.2905	0.008	Significant.
	FEMALE	43	3.074	.4494			
Wage	MALE	57	3.400	.5769	0.3488	0.001	Significant.
	FEMALE	43	3.051	.4495			
Financial	MALE	57	3.207	.4750	0.2396	0.008	Significant.
	FEMALE	43	2.967	.4069			
Overall	MALE	57	3.147	.4555	0.1895	0.028	Significant.
	FEMALE	43	2.957	.3898			

Table 7: Differences on the Impact According to Profile

A pair of pairs are made to determine the effectiveness of the genre of real estate materials. There is no significant effect on sales (average in male = 2.747 and average in women = 2.758; SD (Standard Deviation) in male = .5392 and SD in female = 0.4812) and on revenue (average in south = 3.014 and an average of 2.935; SD in male = 0.4373 and SD in female = 0.3696). On the other hand, the comparison of post-hoc tests are indicated in (average in the south = 3.365 and average in women = 3.074; SD in male = 0.6212 and SD in female = 0.4494), in the bar Math of wages (average salary = 3.400 and female vehicles = 3.051; SD in male = .5769 and SD in female = 0.4495), financial conditions (average in south = 3.207 and average in Female = 2.967; SD in male = 0.4750 and SD in female = .4069). For the overall results of this category, there is a

significant effect between the resort owner of women and men. It is shown that there are a bigger number of individuals in men who answer the survey than women. The results show that some are insignificant, and others are not. Substantial results show that there is a difference if the sexes are different. It is mainly based on how they do their work and think about their strategies on how to market their business. Although the results are not significant, the sex differences are not significant based on this category. Related results (Kuppuswamy and Mollick, 2019) men are more likely to try but otherwise, try to increase numbers. Women again, more and more incompatible are less likely to retry than men. In short, men have more people who accept more than women. Strategic men than women.

B. In Terms of Age

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	MeanSquare	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Sales	Between Groups	4.452	3	1.484	6.608	.000	Significant.
	Within Groups	21.558	96	.225			
	Total	26.010	99				
Revenue	Between Groups	2.513	3	.838	5.708	.001	Significant.
	Within Groups	14.087	96	.147			
	Total	16.600	99				
Employment	Between Groups	13.323	3	4.441	22.633	.000	Significant.
	Within Groups	18.837	96	.196			
	Total	32.160	99				
Wage	Between Groups	12.935	3	4.312	24.100	.000	Significant.
	Within Groups	17.175	96	.179			
	Total	30.110	99				
Financial	Between Groups	4.952	3	1.651	9.875	.000	Significant.
	Within Groups	16.047	96	.167			
	Total	20.998	99				
Overall	Between Groups	4.562	3	1.521	10.196	.000	Significant.
	Within Groups	14.317	96	.149			
	Total	18.879	99				

Table 8

There is a significant effect on age. After comparing the learning test is indicated in the general result between groups (Square Average = 1.521 and $F = 10.196$) and in the groups (average square = .149 and $f = 10.196$). For the overall results of this list, there is a significant impact on the age of the owner of the complex. Each type of table acts a significant part in this study and each result of data collected in this study. Researchers want to determine the superior person when it comes to this list. Also, to differentiate how people of their age think about strategies

to make their businesses even more successful. However, we know that young business owners and old business owners think, act, and act differently. The findings relate (Eitel, 2019) to the fact that "young business owners create a third of new businesses, and these businesses will grow rapidly if they survive," the researchers said. "New businesses started by old business owners are more likely to survive but may not perform as well – grow more slowly and are less likely to hire."

C. In terms of educational attainment

T-TEST

Educational Attainment		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	p-value	Interpretation
Sales	Bachelor's Degree	66	2.870	.4992	0.3462	0.001	Significant.
	Master's degree	34	2.524	.4645			
Revenue	Bachelor's Degree	66	2.964	.4281	-0.0481	0.580	Not Significant.
	Master's degree	34	3.012	.3748			
Employment	Bachelor's Degree	66	3.118	.5108	-0.3583	0.005	Significant.
	Master's degree	34	3.476	.6110			
Wage	Bachelor's Degree	66	3.109	.4787	-0.4144	0.001	Significant.
	Master's degree	34	3.524	.5868			
Financial	Bachelor's Degree	66	3.048	.4548	-0.1633	0.096	Not Significant.
	Master's degree	34	3.212	.4591			
Overall	Bachelor's Degree	66	3.022	.4316	-0.1259	0.167	Not Significant.
	Master's degree	34	3.149	.4406			

Table 9

TTEST couples are made to determine the effects of learning about complex owners. There is a significant effect on sales (average in Bacculaureate = 2.870 and Mastery average = 2.524; SD in a bachelor's degree in Bachelor = .4992 and SD in Mastery level = .4645). Although in revenue, there is no significant effect (Means of Bacculaureate = 2.964 and Mastery Medium = 3.012; SD in Bachelor = .4281 and SD in Mastery degree = .3748). There is a significant effect on employment (talent vehicles = 3.118 and average in control = 3.476; SD in bachelor's degree = .5108 and SD Master's degree = 0.6110) and payment salary (middle Binh Tu Tai = 3.109 and average in control = 3.524; SD in a bachelor's degree on Bachelor = .4787 and SD control Mastery = 0.5868). Although in the financial situation, but there is no significant effect (talent vehicles = 3.048 and average in control = 3.212; SD at the Bachelor level = .4548 and SD in the master level = .4591). For the overall results for this category, there was no significant effect between educational level versus the owner of beach resorts. The results show that some are insignificant, and others are not. Substantial results demonstrate that there is a difference if an individual reaches a certain type of educational attainment, it considers a particular kind of activity in their work and on how they carry out and have an understanding. Although the results were not significant, differences in an individual's education level were not significant based on this classification. The

results are linked (trends in a series of entrepreneurs, 2020) that about fifty-one percent (51%) of tycoons have a bachelor's degree and the proportion of businesspersons with a bachelor's degree is high in most Asian businesspersons (29.6%).

V. DISCUSSION

When researchers in this study have checked the results, they understand that to help research improvement, it is very useful to promote current companies. Promoting and keeping your business living in a pandemic is difficult. Adapt to such modern ways on how to promote and encourage visitors to the facility. By using social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube), creating attractive commercial videos and invitations can increase the current activity. Attracting customers by reducing some money. In addition, providing promotions for guests who have experienced this will encourage other visitors to visit. Because it also increases sales and financial conditions and revenue of a slow business. And at that time, if the situation was sent, the owner of the terminal will eventually begin to get the position of sales and finance and its total revenue much more.

Improving the safety of health and the implementation of the best practices for employees is safe, which is also a major factor. Identify medical and safe

measures that are needed to prevent subsequent transmission. Business owners should implement necessary safety distance practices. Using gloves, plexiglass barriers, providing a variety of alcohol in the facility, strict by informing customers to keep their masks, which forces them to check its temperature before entering the installation Set, etc., therefore there will be no problems or problems with problems if any problems are guests who will visit this place. At least they know that complexes follow the protocols and visitors feel safe within the facility. Station owners should also have a backup plan for employees who have been quarantined. They should be prepared for the worst-case scenario if most workers are quarantined for prolonged exposure. The preparation of work schedules, communication plans (including employees, customers, suppliers), and the number of isolation days must be clear. For this, there will be no complications, especially about the wages of workers, especially if they do not work on a certain day. Resort owners need to carefully craft a clear and concise message, plan regular updates, and optimize technology to deliver the message. Also, it will be more organized and clearer to employees because they are the ones to be exposed, especially if the time comes, and everything will be back to normal. Assigning someone you trust to do this is a particularly important task.

Finally, station owners should develop an ongoing weekly cash flow plan. It is better to anticipate business losses and prepare a solution than to not find the means to achieve it. Having specific and solid strategies and combining them in a cash flow plan will help businesses determine the exact amount of working capital needed. Presenting a list of weekly week's cash flows is a must. It should be updated at the beginning and the end of each week because the cash flow plans act as a fuel measure for a company. Money is fuel for each company; a Cash flow plan is a measure of the amount of working capital needed to achieve behavioral objectives. List cash flow, cash flow and analyze the cash flow forecast so that the situation is monitored in the case of a problem. And if there is a problem encountered, it's easy to act and place a solution because it is updated every week.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study is designed to help the economy of the tourist area in this situation, especially in Indang, Cavite, by conducting a survey and assessing the situation to take a long-term planned action. The first part of the study presents the number of respondents that filled out an online survey about the economic impact of Covid-19 restrictions on the resort industry in Indang, Cavite. Gender, Age, and Educational Attainment are the three categories on the responders' profile. It shows different percentages of how every single one of them is different from one another. The second part of the paper presents the body of the paper: Sales, Revenue, Employment, Wage Payment, and financial conditions. This paper shows different percentages and data about the five categories when it comes to the performances of each resort in Indang Cavite. Some are high percentages, and

some are low but to summarize all are significant to the whole study of this research. Also, to conclude Indang is having a challenging time recovering because of the damage of the pandemic. As an effect, there are big adjustments to be implemented just for the business to continue, especially tourism sites like resort industries. But even though the pandemic happened, they used the time to improve their facilities resulting in a secure economic condition. With the profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment, most of them have a master's degree which shows that they are knowledgeable in terms of owning and managing a resort.

The most complicated issue we face in this crisis is finding the correct balance between preventing not only the damage caused by Covid-19 but also the damage caused by a substantial downturn of economic activity. A severe recession is likely to cause widespread suffering, including higher mortality rates due to causes other than the virus, making this a question of life and death, as well as prosperity or poverty. As a result, we must devise clever techniques for reopening enterprises while reducing health concerns. Make sales the focal point of your plan. This may have worked well enough in a good economy, but in a tight market, look to your sales function to win business. Sales are where strategy is put into action, as it connects all your offerings to the market. Your sales strategy, sales experience, and customer contacts can emerge from the epidemic stronger than ever with smart revisions, planning, and a little innovation. Create policies and procedures for social distancing, hygiene, cleaning, and general operations. Employees should be educated in new policies and procedures. Make sure you have all the tools and resources you will need to reopen securely. Website, when clients search for you, update the sites so that your reopening plans and practices are evident. If your website offers live chat, you might wish to have an automatic message appear that summarizes the most valuable information. Channels on social media create a series of posts for each platform of business utilizes and distribute them regularly in the weeks leading up to your reopening and during your first few weeks back in operation. Frequent updates on your team and operations will demonstrate to your employees that you are open to business and actively responding to their requirements. Always keep an open mind. Do not get caught up in the perpetual flux. Consider everything that might be able to help you improve your situation. Make a list of all you are capable of. While most of what happened during the epidemic were out of your hands, it is vital to remember that you may always have an impact on things. We are in a unique situation where we must act quickly and socially responsibly while constantly ensuring the safety of our customers and employees.

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